

counted. Nematode population was determined by thoroughly mixing the soil in each bucket, then taking a 250-cc soil sample for extraction using Baermann's

funnel method.

All rates of carbofuran significantly reduced nematode population. Early application of 2 kg ai/ha performed best.

For late application, 3 kg ai/ha is suggested. There was no phytotoxicity at that rate. □

Entomostracan crustaceans inhabiting rice fields

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We collected 100 samples of aquatic fauna from the rice fields in and around Ludhiana in 1982 summer, and identified species of Entomostraca. There were 2 conchostracans, 4 cladocerans, 15 ostracods, and 6 copepods (see table). □

Entomostraca from rice fields at Ludhiana, India.

Species	Order/Family
<i>Cyclestheria hislopi</i> (Barid)	Order Conchstraca Family Cyclestheriidae
<i>Caenesthereilla indica</i> (Gurney)	Family Cyzicidae
<i>Diaphanosoma sarsi</i> Richard	Order Cladocera Family Sididae
<i>Leydigia acanthocercoides</i> (Fischer)	Family Chydoridae
<i>Moina brachiata</i> (Jurine)	Family Monidae
<i>Macrothrix hirsuticornis</i> Norman and Brady	Family Macrothricidae
<i>Centrocypris bhagirathiae</i> Battish	Class Ostracoda
<i>C. madani</i> Battish	Family Cyprididae
<i>Cypris pubera</i> Muller	
<i>Cypris subglobosa</i> Sowerby	
<i>Cyprinotus cingalensis</i> Brady	
<i>Hemicypris derweshensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris malerkotlaensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris pyxidata</i> (Moniez)	
<i>Strandesia elongata</i> Hartmann	
<i>Chrissia</i> sp.	
<i>Stenocypris major</i> (Baird)	
<i>Ilyocypris biphlicata</i> (Koch)	
<i>I. bradyi</i> Sars	
<i>I. dentifera</i> Sars	
<i>I. gibba</i> (Ramdohr)	
<i>Eucyclops speratus</i> (Lilljeborg)	Class Copepoda Order Cyclopoida
<i>Mesocyclops leuckarti</i> (Claus)	
<i>M. tenuis</i> (Marsh)	
<i>Microcyclops dentatimanus</i> (Marsh)	
<i>M. varicans</i> (Sars)	
<i>Phyllodiptomus blanci</i> (Guerne and Richard)	Order Calanoida

Soil and crop management

Residual effects of straw, lime, and manganese dioxide amendments on the chemical kinetics of a flooded iron-toxic soil

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Fertilizer shortages and high fertilizer prices have encouraged research to determine the residual effect of various amendments applied to improve problem soils. To estimate the beneficial and economic effects of CaCO₃, MnO₂, and straw amendments, we need to know how long the residual effects will persist.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to determine the residual effects of straw (2.5 g/kg soil), CaCO₃ (2.5 g/kg soil), MnO₂ (0.05 g/kg soil) amendments. Soil was collected from the top 20 cm of a Sulfaquept from Malinao, Albay, Philippines. It had pH 3.4, 0.64% organic C, 0.04% total N, 2.4% active Fe, and 0.003% active Mn²⁺. Four 3-wk-old seedlings were transplanted in each Pot in 4 replications, and the soil solution was analyzed every 2 wk.

Straw and CaCO₃ treatment depressed Eh, EC, Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, and SO₄²⁻

Kinetics of soil solution Fe⁺⁺ as affected by the different residual treatments, IRRI.

concentrations in the soil solution and increased pH. When the straw was combined with CaCO₃, they strongly reduced Fe²⁺ (see figure) and SO₄²⁻ concentrations in the soil solution.

The MnO₂ treatment gave a high residual level of Mn²⁺ in the soil solution compared to other treatments, slightly decreased the Eh, EC, Fe²⁺, SO₄²⁻ contents, and increased the pH of the soil solution compared to the control.

Straw and CaCO₃ residual effects increased plant height and tiller number up to 4 wk after transplanting (WT) compared to other treatments and the control. Poor plant growth of the control and MnO₂ residual treatments was related to high Fe²⁺ in the soil solution. At 4 WT, the residual treatment of straw + CaCO₃ had lower soil solution Fe²⁺ concentrations than the other residual treatments. Plants had greater shoot dry weight and better Fe toxicity scores than in other treatments.

At 6-8 WT, the concentration of Fe²⁺ decreased gradually in MnO₂ and control treatments. That caused vigorous plant growth and higher straw and grain yields/pot than other treatments. However, the differences in grain yields among treatments were not significant (see table).

Yield of grain and straw of IR26 on an iron-toxic soil, IRR1.

Treatment	Yield ^a (g/pot)	
	Grain	Straw
	<i>1st crop</i>	
	<i>Dried 2 wk presubmergence</i>	
Control	4 d	5 c
MnO ₂ (0.005%)	25 c	21 b
Straw (0.25%)	28 c	23 b
MnO ₂ (0.005%) + straw (0.25%)	38 bc	34 a
CaCO ₃ (0.25%)	55 a	44 a
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + MnO ₂ (0.005%)	56 a	45 a
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + straw (0.25%)	40 abc	41 a
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + MnO ₂ (0.005%) + straw (0.25%)	52 ab	41 a
	<i>2d crop</i>	
	<i>Continuously submerged</i>	
Control	38 a	106 a
MnO ₂ (0.005%)	34 a	78 b
Straw (0.25%)	31 a	48 c
MnO ₂ (0.005%) + straw (0.25%)	30 a	40 c
CaCO ₃ (0.25%)	21 a	26 c
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + MnO ₂ (0.005%)	22 a	28 c
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + straw (0.25%)	23 a	30 c
CaCO ₃ (0.25%) + MnO ₂ (0.25%) + straw (0.25%)	22 a	28 c

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

This experiment showed that the residual effect of the soil treatments, especially CaCO₃ and CaCO₃ combinations, substantially reduced straw yields, possibly because of exhaustive nutrient uptake by the first crop. The yield in the control, however, increased tremendously after prolonged submergence because

the toxicity constraints were remedied and nutrients were not limited. Prolonged submergence remedied iron toxicity, resulting in increased yields. The negative residual effects of lime and straw amendments on a second crop of rice when the soil is kept submerged has still to be elucidated. □

Response of rice to nitrogen, phosphorus, and zinc in sodic soil

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We studied the response of P2-21 to N, P, and Zn application in a barren sodic soil at Gudda Farm in 1980 and 1981. Soil was sandy loam with pH 10.4, 93% exchangeable sodium, 0.22 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g, 0.2% total N, 9.8 Olsen's extractable P, 0.34 ppm DTPA Zn, and adequate available K in the 0-15 cm layer.

Gypsum at 13.25 t/ha was uniformly broadcast in 1980 and incorporated at 10-cm depth. Fields had standing water for 15 d before transplanting. Rice was transplanted on 18 Jul in 1980 and 10

Jul in 1981. P, Zn, and 1/2 N were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in equal splits 25 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). N, P, and Zn were applied as urea, superphosphate, and zinc sulfate.

The rice grain and straw yields in all treatments were significantly superior to those of the no-fertilizer control in both

years. In 1980, grain and straw yields did not increase from combined application of N and P or N and Zn over N alone, but yields were significantly higher with N, P, and Zn (see table).

In 1981, the yields were significantly higher with N, P, and Zn and N and P. There was also no significant yield difference between N alone and N and Zn. □

Yield attributes and grain and straw yield with different fertilizer applications, Karnal, India.

Treatment	Productive tillers/hill	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)							
			Grain		Straw					
			1980	1981	1980	1981				
N	P	Zn	1980	1981	1980	1981				
0	0.0	0	6	9	18	19	0.6	1.2	0.8	1.6
120	0.0	0	19	19	19	20	2.8	3.7	3.1	4.5
120	0.0	6	18	20	20	20	3.2	3.7	3.4	4.6
120	26.8	0	18	22	20	20	3.0	4.6	3.3	5.4
120	26.8	6	23	26	20	21	3.9	4.7	4.4	5.5
CD (P = 0.05)			3.9	3.5	1.1	1.9	0.5	0.2	0.9	0.2